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Research Paper

Elucidation of Anti-Bacterial Potential of *Argemone Mexicana*

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants have historically played a crucial role in treating infectious diseases. *Argemone Mexicana* L., commonly found in desolate regions of Maharashtra, has been traditionally used for its medicinal properties. This study elucidates the anti-bacterial potential of *Argemone Mexicana* extracts against *Escherichia coli* and compares it with turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) extract. The results confirm the promising antibacterial activity of *A. Mexicana*, supporting its potential use in the development of alternative antimicrobial therapies.

INTRODUCTION

Nature offers countless plants with hidden medicinal properties, and *Argemone Mexicana*, often overlooked as a wild weed, stands out with significant therapeutic potential. This spiny annual herb, when cut, releases a yellow latex rich in biologically active compounds. Traditionally, various parts of *A. Mexicana* have been used to treat skin diseases, respiratory issues, ulcers, and more. Amidst rising antibiotic resistance, plant-based treatments gain renewed interest for their safety and efficacy.¹⁻⁵

Objectives:

1. To prepare aqueous extracts of *Argemone Mexicana*.
2. To evaluate and compare the anti-bacterial activity against *E. coli*.
3. to benchmark its efficacy with turmeric extracts.⁶⁻¹⁰

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Figure no. 01: Plant Image, Stem, Flower, Leaves, Fruits and Seeds of *A. Mexicans*.

Literature Review: Several studies have demonstrated *A. Mexicans* antimicrobial activity against pathogenic bacteria including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Bacillus subtilis*.¹¹⁻¹⁵ Various extraction methods using solvents like methanol, hexane, and aqueous preparations have confirmed its broad-spectrum potential due to its alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds.

Plant Profile:

Botanical Name: *Argemone Mexicana* L.

Family: Papaveraceae

Common Names: Mexican Poppy, Pila Dhatura, Phirangi Dhotra

Active Constituents: Berberine, Protopine, Pancorin, Oxyberberin, Alkaloids, Flavonoids.

Medicinal Uses: Antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, expectorant.¹⁶⁻²³

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Plant Collection and Preparation: Fresh leaves were collected, washed with distilled water, shade-dried, and ground into powder.

Extraction: Using Soxhlet extraction with ethanol as solvent, concentrated extract was obtained and stored for analysis.

Figure no. 02: Collection and preparation of *A. Mexicana*.

Figure no. 03: Soxhlet extraction and evaporation of aqueous extract of *A. Mexicana*.

Anti-Bacterial Assay: Agar Well Diffusion Method was employed using nutrient agar inoculated with *E. coli*. Wells were filled with varying concentrations of *A. Mexicana* extract,

turmeric extract (positive control), and distilled water (negative control). Zones of inhibition were measured after 24 and 48 hours.

Figure no. 04: Preparation of nutrient agar medium for *A. Mexicana*.

Figure no. 05: Zone of Inhibition after 24 hrs.

Figure no. 06: Zone of Inhibition after 48 hrs.

RESULT

The antibacterial activity of *Argemone Mexicana* extract and turmeric extract was evaluated against *Escherichia coli* by measuring the Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) after 24 and 48 hours.

For the *Argemone Mexicana* extract:

- At 4% concentration, the ZOI was 10 mm after 24 hours and 11 mm after 48 hours.
- At 8% concentration, the ZOI was 13 mm after 24 hours and 14 mm after 48 hours.
- At 12% concentration, the ZOI was 16 mm after 24 hours and 17 mm after 48 hours.

For the turmeric extract:

- At 4% concentration, the ZOI was 18 mm after 24 hours and 20 mm after 48 hours.
- At 8% concentration, the ZOI was 21 mm after 24 hours and 23 mm after 48 hours.
- At 12% concentration, the ZOI was 24 mm after 24 hours and 26 mm after 48 hours.

The water (negative control) showed no antibacterial activity, with a Zone of Inhibition of 0 mm at both 24 and 48 hours.

Table no. 01: Result of Zone of inhibition after 24 and 48 hrs of different extract:

Treatment	Volume (µL)	ZOI after 24 hr (mm)	ZOI after 48 hr (mm)
<i>Argemone Mexicana</i> extract	4 %	10	11
	8 %	13	14
	12 %	16	17
Turmeric extract	4 %	18	20
	8 %	21	23
	12 %	24	26
Water (Control)	-	0	0

DISCUSSION

The study demonstrated a dose-dependent antibacterial effect of *Argemone Mexicana* extracts. Although turmeric exhibited a larger inhibition zone, the extract of *A. Mexicana* also significantly inhibited bacterial growth. The activity is attributed to its rich content of secondary metabolites like alkaloids and flavonoids.

CONCLUSION

Both *Argemone Mexicana* and turmeric extracts showed significant antibacterial activity against *E. coli*. This supports the potential use of *Argemone Mexicana* as a natural antimicrobial agent. Further research including MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentration) determination and phytochemical studies is recommended.

Marketed Preparations:

- Pure Organic Mexican Poppy Tablets – Skin diseases, microbial infections
- Yogimate Poppy Seed Powder – Digestive aid, respiratory support
- SBL *Argemone Mexicana* Dilution – Skin and liver support
- Argemone Mother Tincture – Respiratory and digestive aid
- Natural Herbs Poppy Seeds – Digestive and liver health booster.

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Ethical Approval:

This review article does not content of any use of animal model.

Conflict of Interest:

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